

Create and Design Visual Presentation to Promote Thai Cuisine

Supaporn Wimonchailerk

Abstract—This research aims to study how to design and create the media to promote Thai cuisine. The study used qualitative research methods by using in-depth interview 3 key informants who have experienced in the production of food or cooking shows in television programs with an aspect of acknowledging Thai foods. The results showed that visual presentation is divided into four categories. First, the light meals should be presented in details via the close-up camera with lighting to make the food look more delicious. Then the curry presentation should be arranged a clear and crisp light focus on a colorful curry paste. Besides the vision of hot steam floating from the plate and a view of curry spread on steamed rice can call great attentions. Third, delivering good appearances of the fried or spicy foods, the images must allow the audiences to see the shine of the coat covering the texture of the food and the colorful of the ingredients. Fourth, the presentation of sweets is recommended to focus on details of food design, composition, and layout.

Keywords— Media production, television, promote, Thai cuisine.

I. INTRODUCTION

THAILAND has established the policy of the Government on the Thai Cuisine to the World or "Krua Thai Su Krua Loke" according to the rising numbers of food exported to the world making hundreds of millions of Thai baht each year, and the year 2012 was the first year the export value of Thailand achieved the trillions. In addition, the five years afterward target is that in the year 2017, the output value expected to reach 2 trillion Thai baht as an impact of transforming ASEAN Economic Community (AEC) envisions ASEAN as a single market from 2015.

Thai foods found to be good driving matters that creates income for farmers in the local community as its ingredients such as vegetables, meat, as well as spices were naturally growth by the agriculturists in the country. The popularity of Thai dishes is obvious. There are many tourists travel to Thailand to taste authentic of Thai cuisine. Some of them even took cooking classes in Thailand evidenced by increasing numbers of Thai cooking schools. Many hotels have also prepared a cooking course to facilitate their customers. There are many Thai dishes that famous among the foreigners such as Tom-Yum Kung, Pad Thai, Green curry and much more.

The researchers, therefore, found its importance of promoting Thai cuisine through the medias by emphasizing study on local.

Objective of this research is how to design and create the media to promote Thai cuisine

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The research framework was designed to study how to create and design visual presentation to promote Thai cuisine from the specialists in the production of food or cooking shows in television programs

The research had led to developing communication concepts with many theories include a media production concept and AIDA model to apply as a framework for this research. The researchers have put forward the integration and the established framework of concept to this research as follow.

Fig. 1 Conception framework: how to design the presentation to promote Thai food on Television Program

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

The study of Create and Design Visual Presentation to Promote Thai Cuisine, the researchers conducted a literature review of relevant concepts and theories to adopt a framework and approach to the educational aspects. It can be classified into the following sub-topics.

A. Concepts and Theories of Communications

Communication is to provide and receive information, understand and awareness. This is the concept of interactivity which shares and interact with each other. Duangporn Kumnoonwat (2007) [1] expresses an ideal effective communication that it contains the good communicators filled with knowledge related to the topics, understand the objectives of contents delivered, know the variety of communication channels including the natures of each media and know insight the audiences. Beside the communicators must realize their own capability.

B. Media Production Concepts

Producing each type of media has its own aim of publishing such as teaching documents, PR publicity, etc. They have an extensive range of activities related to people and funding. The scope and size of the project are not only the important factors, the overall resources and the systematic production also crucial need to be well organized by the producers [2, p.1-5].

The systematic media production is used 3W1 as the fundamental concept planning which initiates the creation. The producer, therefore, needs to answer these 4 questions clearly. First, "Why" asking about the aim of the production. Second, "Who" asking about the direct audients. Then, "What" asking the main content presented in the media. Last, "How" the question asking about which publication or sorts of media that suitable to the contents of the presentation.

C. AIDA Model

AIDA Model is the response generated by the response from the audience with 4 sequenced steps which are 1) "A" stand for attention; the media exposure can attract attention at first sight. The audience can feel the attention and intentions to the media. 2) "I" stand for interest that the media can create interest information and understanding to the audience by making a difference and novelty of the media which lead to interest to follow. 3) "D" stand for a desire that refers to the media, urging the audience's satisfaction and more attraction that cause the demands and lead to actions. 4) "A" from action which media can encourage the audience to act in responses [3]-[5].

III. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

This research is qualitative research. The research is divided into two parts.

A. Part I: Media to Promotes Thai Foods

1. Informants

In this study, key informants comprising from 3 experts of television producers who were specifically selected as samples of professional television production professionals. In order to analyze the media that promotes Thai foods and improves the media to promote Thai cuisine.

2. Data Collecting Tools

In-depth interviews were used as data collecting tools for this study. The interview questions were designed to ask about the media to promote Thai foods which divide into four categories of foods. Notes and the interview tape are also recorded during the interview.

3. Data Analysis

The research data from tape recordings of the interviews were recorded and analyzed as descriptive data in order to analyze the media to promote Thai dishes. Then conclude and find ways to improve the production and design o media to promote Thailand.

B. Part2 : Evaluation of a New Designed Media Production for Thai Foods Promoting

1. Informants

In this part of the study, there are 10 primary informants, consisting of 5 experts of television programs who selected by purposive sampling. The qualifications are mainly considering the 3 years experienced in the information and media producing. And then the rest of 5 general samples who selected by purposive sampling which considering the samples with full experience and a passion for Thai foods.

2. Data Collecting Tools

Data collecting tools of this part of the study is individual interviews which use a newly designed media to test and ask the question during the interview. There are questions about the effectiveness of the design AIDA Model with a note and taped the interview recorded.

3. Data Analysis

The researchers collect the details from the recorded notes of the in-depth interview of 10 informants to divide into 2 groups; the media professionals and the general samples.

The data were descriptively analyzed by critical analyzing the types of information under the consideration of AIDA Model systematic production. To get attractions, interests which lead to highly demanded and cause of action.

IV. RESULT AND DISCUSSIONS

A. Part I: Presentation Media to Promotes Thai Foods

In this study of presenting media to promote Thai foods, Thai dishes were divided into 4 categories: light meals, curries, fried or spicy foods and desserts. The media presentation is divided into three areas.

1. Size of Image to Present Thai Cuisine

All four categories of Thai dishes; light meals, curries, fried or spicy foods and desserts should present as a close-up image focus on a profile on details of foods, shooting angle in the top view. The curry dishes should be emphasized on the presentation of the concentration of curry spices.

The fried or spicy foods should display and present the shadow of the food allow the audience to see the shine of the coat covering the texture of the food and the colorful of the ingredients. The presentation of the cooking procedures should also be brought up to make the audience feel the interest to imagine the scents and flavors.

2. Managing Light for Thai Food Presentation

Presenting food with light is a crucial way to make the dish more mouth-watering. The producer should manage to have crisp, clear light to give a better look to the foods. In addition, taking a good shot of curry dishes must prepare for a vision of hot steam floating from the plate on dark colors background which recommends as a technique to be used.

3. Thai Foods Display, and Layout

Arranging of plate decorative props such as plate, bowl,

spoons and forks, tablecloths and etc. are also important to make the food looks more delicious.

4. Designing Outcomes

From the result in part 1, the researcher can conclude the direction of designing and presenting media to present Thai foods to be a motion picture with the length of 3-minutes time.

Fig. 2 Shooting angle at the top view of Thai light meal (Savory Leaf Wrap or Miang Kham)

Fig. 3 A close up image focus on a profile on details of Thai light meal (Savory Leaf Wrap or Miang Kham)

Fig. 4 Shooting angle at the top view of Thai light meal (Sour prawn soup or Tom Yum Kung)

Fig. 5 A close-up image of Thai curry (Sour prawn soup or Tom Yum Kung)

Fig. 6 Shooting angle at the top view of fried (Thai Fried Noodles or Phat Thai)

Fig. 7 A close up image focus on a profile on details of fried (Thai Fried Noodles or Phat Thai)

Fig. 8 Shooting angle at the top view off of Thai desserts (Thong yot, Met Khanoon, and foithong)

Fig. 9 A close-up image focus on a profile on details of Thai desserts (Thong yot, Met Khanoon and foithong)

B. Part II: Evaluation of a New Designed Media Production for Thai Foods Promoting

1. AIDA Model

A. Attention

This media, the video presentation is interesting because of the opening with an image of foods. The movement of the camera and transition of images in each category make the

vision of the food illustrated nicely and smoothly. Consistent with the results of [3] which claim that media can call attention at first sight and make communicator intended to generate interest and media exposure.

B. Interest

The Transition of images in each category is presented without interruption. Each food types have its different strengths which allow the viewers to watch from the beginning to the end. Consistent with the results of [3] which refer to the media attention and understanding to the audience by making a difference and novelty of the media which lead to the interest to follow.

C. Desire

The video media is well satisfied as it allows the audiences to acknowledge the popular Thai dish via the motion pictures presentation that easy to understand for the audience with all ages. This satisfaction leads to interesting and the desire to consume Thai foods as an action. Consistent with the results of [3] which state that the media, urging the audience's satisfaction and more attraction that cause the demands and lead to actions

D. Action

This media can help stimulate the desire to consume Thai foods. As it is an interesting motion picture which appeal and consistent with the results of [3] indicated that the media could encourage audience response behavior.

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